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CONTENTS

Sr. No.	Author	Title of the Paper	Pg.No.	Download
INDIAN LITERATURE				
01	Ashly Thomas	Interrogating Casteism: An Althusserian Reading of Sharankumar Limbale's <i>Akkarmashi The Outcaste</i>	01-17	PDF
02	Atish Chandrakant Akade	Theory of Purushartha: Girish Karnad's <i>Bali: The Sacrifice</i>	18-21	PDF
03	Debanjana Nayek	The Experience of	22-26	PDF

		Trauma in Two Indian Graphic Novels, <i>Delhi Calm</i> and <i>River of Stories</i>		
04	Dr. Deepak Kumar & Anita Goswami	Bharati Mukherjee's <i>Jasmine</i> : Cultural Dichotomy and Rootlessness	27-35	PDF
05	Jayanta Rana	Performing Dissent: Rape Narratives in Manjula Padmanabhan's <i>Lights Out!</i> (1984)	36-44	PDF
06	Karuna Sharma	Comparative Study of Eastern and Western Culture in the Novels of Vikram Seth	45-53	PDF
07	Konjengbam Maheshwari	Theatre, Politics and Heishnam Kanhailal's <i>Pebet</i> : A Study	54-58	PDF
08	Manjeet Kumar Rai	Across the Threshold of Hetero-normative Culture: <i>A Married Woman</i> by Manju Kapur	59-63	PDF
09	Manoj D. Gujar	Identity Crisis in Shashi Deshpande's <i>That Long Silence</i>	64-70	PDF
10	Dr. Vinita Singh Chawdhry & Meenakshi Bhadra	Cross Cultural Confrontations in the Writings of Bharati Mukherjee	71-77	PDF
11	Nadia Shah	An Aesthetics of Mystical Poetry: A Study of Bimla Raina's <i>The Silence Within</i>	78-81	PDF
12	Nandini Baruah	The Female Voice in the Novels of Mamoni Roisom Goswami: Ushered in of a New Era of	82-85	PDF

		Women Empowerment		
13	Dr. Bharati Patnaik	Oppressed and Marginalized Women in Vijay Tendulkar's <i>Kamala</i>	86-89	PDF
14	Payam Bhadraiah	The Voice of Colonized in M.K. Gandhi's <i>Hind Swaraj</i>	90-94	PDF
15	T. Pushpanathan	Girish Karnad as the Mirror of Indian Theatrical Identity	95-98	PDF
16	P. Rishi Iniyar	Re-visiting 'Home': A Study of the Return-Home Narratives of Bharati Mukherjee and Meena Alexander	99-103	PDF
17	Rushika Gill	Literature and Identity: The Portrayal of Female Struggle for Identity	104-108	PDF
18	Saikat Banerjee	Inter-caste and Class Conflicts in Kartar Singh Duggal's Selected Short Stories	109-113	PDF
19	Sameer Ahmad Shah	Ordeal, Agony and Anxiety: Exploring the Pandit Exile through <i>Our Moon Has Blood Clots</i>	114-117	PDF
20	Dr. Shравan Kumar & Dr. Harleen Kaur	Post Colonialism: Meaning and its Impact With Special Reference of the Writings of Ann Bhalla	118-123	PDF
21	Sini Femiz	Social Injustice Reflected In Mulk Raj Anand's <i>Untouchable</i>	124-128	PDF

22	Dr. S. Alexander & Siva Vidhya. M	Existentialism in Kamala Markandaya's <i>Nectar In A Sieve</i>	129-136	PDF
23	Srideep Mukherjee	'The Concert of Womanhood': Reading Nandini Sahu's <i>Sita</i> (A Poem)	137-150	PDF
BRITISH LITERATURE				
01	Binoy Dangar	Shelley, the Mythmaker	151-154	PDF
02	Shweta Chaudhary	<i>Othello</i> : A Comedy of Characters, Situation and Dialogues	155-165	PDF
03	Niharika Singh	<i>The Caretaker</i> : Challenges and Confrontations	166-171	PDF
04	P. Parthiban & Dr. S. Alexander	Satan, the Anti-God Functionally the Fourth Person, Supervising the Spiritual Progress of Humanity: William Blake's Views from the Holy Bible	172-185	PDF
05	Dr. Piyushbala	A Study of Gender and Humanism in Shakespeare's Drama	186-192	PDF
06	Sunita Dhankhar	The Silent Voices: Enigma of Naipaul's Female Characters	193-200	PDF
07	Dr. B. Vasanthakumar	Hero's Destiny in Fantasy Literature	201-204	PDF
08	Vibha Dwivedi	Thomas Hardy's Female Characters Represent the Problem of Contemporary Victorian Society	205-211	PDF
AMERICAN LITERATURE				
01	Basma Majid	Search for Identity in Alice Walker's <i>The</i>	212-216	PDF

		<i>Color Purple</i>		
02	Dr. Munthar Mohd. Habib	The Theatre of the Absurd and Who is Afraid of Virginia Woolf?	217-221	PDF
03	Ruchi Nigam & Seema Dutta	Surviving the Odds: Women Characters in Khaled Hosseini's <i>A Thousand Splendid Suns</i>	222-227	PDF
04	Dr. Shalini Yadav	Female/ Masculinities and Male/ Femininities: Complexities of Gender Transgression in Leslie Feinberg's <i>Stone Butch Blues</i>	228-234	PDF
05	N. Vaishnavi & Dr. Vishnu Divya	<i>The Women of Brewster Place</i> as a Celebration of Black Feminism	235-239	PDF
CRITICAL THEORY				
01	Dr. Arpita Palchoudhury	Ethnocentrism: Its Implications on Social, Cultural and Workplace Diversity	240-243	PDF
02	B. Gnana Bharathi	The Ethics of Dolphin Tourism in Coco Beach Goa: A Deep Ecology Perspective	244-252	PDF
03	Vaishali Jain	Conceptualization of the <i>Text</i> and the Role of the <i>Reader</i> in Structuralist Poetics	253-262	PDF
04	P. Venkanna (Venkat)	Contemporary Writings in Language and Literature	263-266	PDF
AFRICAN LITERATURE				
01	Asiru Hameed Tunde	Persuasion and/or Manipulation in 'We Must Remain	267-278	PDF

		United’: A 2014 Democracy Day Broadcast by President Goodluck Jonathan		
02	Jamashed Ansari	<i>The Master of Petersburg: A Study of the Conflicts between the Aged and the Young Generations and the Fear of Agedness</i>	279-289	PDF
03	Satheeshraju. Dhenuvakonda & Prof.P.RajendaraKarmarkar	Dichotomy, Achebe’s Fashion of Narration, a Study in <i>No Longer at Ease</i>	290-297	PDF
LANGUAGE & LINGUISTICS				
01	Bharti Rai	The Dismantling of Linguistic Hegemony: An Odyssey to Gender Neutrality in Language	298-305	PDF
02	Samson Mekonnen Hailu	Instructional Technology Based versus Conventional Approach of Teaching Reading Skill: Comparative Study	306-324	PDF
03	Dr. Sandhya Tiwari	Moderation and Facilitation towards a New Horizon in Teaching-Learning Process	325-334	PDF
FILM & LITERATURE				
01	Purvi R. Thaker	Movie Adaptation of Literary Works in Hindi Cinema	335-341	PDF
02	Ritika Pathania	Presentation of Socially Gendered Stereotypes in the Movie- <i>Raincoat</i>	342-349	PDF
03	Satyawan Suresh Mane	A Study of the Dalit	350-	PDF

		Voice in Nagraj Manjule's <i>Fandry</i>	353	
COMPARATIVE LITERATURE				
01	Bhuvaneswari. S	From Enslavement to Emancipation: The Plight of Women as Portrayed by Arundhati Roy and Audrey Thomas	354-358	PDF
02	Nutan Garg	Interrogating 'Home' in National and Transnational Spaces: A Study of Taslima Nasrin's <i>Lajja</i> and Monica Ali's <i>Brick Lane</i>	359-367	PDF
CANADIAN LITERATURE				
01	Tanuka Chatterjee	Alice Munro: The Enduring Storyteller	368-373	PDF
SPANISH LITERATURE				
01	Amechi N. Akwanya	Eros, Thanatos, and Captive Lives in Federico Garcia Lorca's <i>Blood Wedding</i>	374-384	PDF
PAKISTANI LITERATURE				
01	Tehreem Zehra	Agonising Bonds: An Analysis of the Plight of the Tribal Women in Sidhwa's <i>The Pakistani Bride</i>	385-394	PDF
POETRY				
01	Adrienne Christian	Navy Man	395	PDF
02	Andrew Hubbard	Dangerous	396-397	PDF
03	Atul Chandra Sarkar	Incarnation	398	PDF
04	David Kramer	The New Yorker is Publishing My Poem!	399-400	PDF
05	Jeowary Basumatary	A Moment on the Shades of Poetry	401	PDF
06	Jim Newcombe	The Peregrine	402	PDF
07	Ken Williams	Only When the	403-	PDF

		World is Flat	404	
08	Linda Baldanzi	Re:	405	PDF
09	Neelam Dadhwal	Growing Guilt	406	PDF
10	Neha Singh	Untidy	407	PDF
11	Sajal Dey	Haikus from Santiniketan	408-410	PDF
12	Sheri Vandermolen	Maha Shivaratri	411	PDF
13	Tikuli	Lodhi Gardens	412-413	PDF
14	Ramesh Chandra Tiwari	The Human Population	414	PDF
15	Rajesh Dattatray Zankar	Emptiness	415	PDF
FICTION				
01	Anandu Karthikeyan	As Arnab Retires	416-419	PDF
02	Helmi Ben Meriem	The Trilogy of Alfonse	420-425	PDF
03	Ken Williams	2030: "Irreconcilable Differences"	426-427	PDF
04	Naresh Annem	The Radiant Tree	428-434	PDF
05	Pankaj Solanki	Appearances	435-442	PDF
06	Ramesh Chandra Tiwari	God is Even-Handed	443-448	PDF
BOOK REVIEW				
01	Basavaraj Naikar	Gangavva mattu Gangamayi by Dr. Shankar Mokashi-Punekar	449-453	PDF
02	Dr. V. Jaisre	Custody by Manju Kapur	454-455	PDF
03	Prof. N.S.Kullur	Bird in the Sky by Basavaraj Naikar	456-462	PDF
04	Parvathy N	Percy Jackson Series by Rick Riordan	463-467	PDF
INTERVIEW				
01	Ms. Sujata	A Dialogue with Ruskin Bond	468-471	PDF